

Difference in Self, Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement of CBSE School Students on Demographic Variables

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I. Introduction

Academic performance depends on many other factors besides self, emotional and general intelligence. It has been widely assumed that all students at senior level are emotionally mature and intelligent, although it is clear that some students are more successful and perform better than others.

CBSE School

The Board witnessed rapid growth and expansion at the level of Secondary education resulting in improved quality and standard of education in institutions. But with the advent of State Universities and State Boards in various parts of the country the jurisdiction of the Board was confined only to Ajmer, Bhopal and Vindhya Pradesh later. As a result of this, in 1952, the constitution of the Board was amended wherein its jurisdiction was extended to part-C and Part-D territories and the Board was given its present name 'Central Board of Secondary Education'. It was in the year 1962 finally that the Board was reconstituted. The main objectives were to serve the educational institutions more effectively, to be responsive to the educational needs of those students whose parents were employed in the Central Government and had frequently transferable jobs.

Self

Self is best conceived as a system of attitudes towards one self. Just as a person, as a result of experiences, forms attitudes which he organizes into self-consistent system and defends against threats and attacks, so the person also form attitudes towards himself. Self consists of all the perceptions, feelings, attitudes, aspirations and values. Self is the key stone of personality, one cannot imagine a person without self. Self is the essence of personality. Favourable self coincides with favourable personality development. Important characteristics such as emotional stability, self-assertion and self-confidence emerge out of the favourable self.

Emotional Intelligence

Emotional intelligence is a term includes both the aspect of the behaviour, that is, emotions and intelligence. Emotions rule the heart while intelligence rules the brain. Emotional intelligence works on the principal that knowledge and skill may help an individual to get into the situation, but it takes an emotional understanding of self and others to cope up and adjust to it. Thus, Emotional intelligence helps to cope up with the environmental demands and uncertainties.

Mayer and Salovey (1990) recommended the merging of emotions and intelligence under the concept of Emotional Intelligence. They found that several people were superior to others in identifying their own feelings, identifying the feelings of others and solving problems involving emotional issues.

However, it was Daniel Goleman (1995) who popularized the term Emotional Intelligence in his book "Working with Emotional Intelligence". Goleman being the main contributor in the area of emotional intelligence gave some of the important points which are listed as under : (i) IQ plays only 20% to the success of an individual while 80% success is based on one's EI. He observes that many high IQ scoring students have failed in their practical lives, while many average people with higher EI have got phenomenal success. (ii) We have two minds – one an emotional mind that feels and other, a rational mind that thinks. Emotions are fed in to the operations of the rational mind and the rational mind refines the inputs of emotions. (iii) Training programmes can help children to be assertive and to articulate their feelings in situations involving conflict with others. (iv) EI can be taught.

Instead, they should be allowed to see ethics in practice. Furthermore, they should be given different models of ethics so that they may develop their own value conclusions. These viewpoints and ideas propagated by Daniel Goleman have brought a revolution in the field of home, school/college and workplace as it was found that there is something more important than intelligence which contributes to success and that can also be taught and developed through training.

(a) Trait models of Emotional intelligence

Trait model of emotional intelligence focuses on a person's self perceptions of his own emotional abilities. Trait Emotional intelligence comprises of behavioral dispositions and self perceived abilities and thus measured by self reports. In self-report measures, emotional intelligence is measured through emotion related competencies which are manifested in specific traits in the specific situation leading into specific emotional behaviour.

(b) Ability Models of Emotional Intelligence:

The definitions available describes emotional intelligence through four mental abilities ranging from simple to complex, which are, perceiving emotions, using emotions, understanding emotions and managing emotions. Supporters of emotional intelligence as ability say that the best way to measure EI are performance tests. In general, EI ability model of emotional intelligence emphasizes on the cognitive components of emotional intelligence and conceptualizes it by combining feeling with thinking.

Academic Achievement

Academic achievement has been considered as an important factor in the educational life of students. It encourages the students to work hard and learn more. It is the status or level of a person's learning and his ability to apply what he has learned (Pressey & Robinson, 1944). Academic achievement, in general, refers to the scores obtained in the annual examination or refers to the degree or level of success or proficiency attained in some specific area, concerning scholastic or academic work. Academic or educational age, accomplishment quotient or achievement quotient are the most commonly used means to interpret the level of academic achievement of pupils in general or in a specific given subject matter. Academic achievement of the pupils continues to be the primary concern in education and main area of educational research.

II. Review : An Overview

Sridevi and Lisha Parveen (2010) conducted a study on “Relationship of Emotional Intelligence, Adjustment, Self and Scholastic Achievement of Higher Secondary Students”. The findings of the study were: (1) There was a positive relationship among emotional intelligence, adjustment, self-concept and achievement of higher secondary students. (2) Female students possess higher emotional intelligence than male students. (3) There was no significant difference in emotional intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to the type of college in which they are studying.

Drago & Judy (2004) studied “The relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievements in non-traditional college students”. The results demonstrated that emotional intelligence is significantly related to students GPA scores. Student cognitive ability and student age; student anxiety was related to certain emotional intelligence abilities. However, no significant relationship was found between emotional intelligence and achievement motivation. Overall, the results suggest that academic achievement is related to students’ ability to recognize, use and manage their emotions.

Sikhwari, T. D. (2014) conducted a study on the relationship between motivation, self and academic achievement of students at a university in Limpopo Province, South Africa. The study utilized a quantitative cross sectional survey design. A self-constructed questionnaire was used to collect data from a randomly selected sample of second year students representing four schools at the university. The study found that there were significant correlations between self-concept, motivation and academic achievement of students. It was also found that female students are significantly more motivated than their male counterparts. The study concluded that the findings justify the importance of self-concept and motivation to academic achievement.

Statement of the Problem

The study was undertaken with a view to study the differences in the variables, viz., self, emotional intelligence and academic achievement. The study entitled “*Difference in Self, Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement of CBSE School Students on Demographic Variables*”.

Variables

- i. Self
- ii. Emotional Intelligence
- iii. Academic Achievement

Demographic Variables

- i. Gender – Boys / Girls
- ii. Location – Urban / Rural

Objectives of the Study

Following are the objectives formulated in the present study :

1. To study the difference between boys and girls students studying in CBSE schools in self, emotional intelligence and academic achievement.
2. To study the difference between urban and rural students studying in CBSE school in self, emotional intelligence and academic achievement.

Research Hypotheses

Following hypotheses are formulated to realize the above mentioned objectives :

1. There is a significant difference between boys and girls CBSE school students in self, emotional intelligence and academic achievement.
2. There is a significant difference between urban and rural CBSE school students in self, emotional intelligence and academic achievement.

Definitions of Technical Terms

Self

A portion of the phenomenal field gradually becomes differentiated. This is the self. Self denotes, “the organized, consistent conceptual gestalt compose of perception of the characteristics of the ‘I’ or ‘me’ and the perceptions of the relationships of the ‘I’ or ‘me’ to others and to various aspects of life, together with the values attached to these perceptions. It is a gestalt which is available to awareness through not necessarily in awareness. It is a fluid and changing gestalt, a process, but at any given moment it is a specific entity”. The notion of the self refers to a person’s experience as a single, unitary, autonomous being that is separate from others, experienced with continuity through time and place. The experience of the self includes consciousness of one’s physicality as well as one’s inner character and emotional life.

Emotional Intelligence

Various definitions of emotional intelligence were proposed by different psychologists/authors, like Cooper (1996); Bar-On (1997) ; Mayer and Salovey (1997); Goleman (1998); Freedman et al. (1998) ; Singh (2003).But the generalized meaning of emotional intelligence which all the definitions supported is, that emotional intelligence is a unitary ability (related to, but independent of standard intelligence) helpful in knowing, feelings and judging emotions in close cooperation with one’s thinking process to behave in a proper way, for the ultimate realize of the happiness and welfare of the self in tune with others.

Academic Achievement

According to Cosmo Dictionary of Education, “Achievement is a performance in school or college on standardized series of education tests. The term is used more generally to describe performance in the subjects of the curriculum”. Based on past literature, there were numerous definitions of academic achievement. Generally speaking academic achievement was defined as “a student’s academic performance in school” (Chen 2007). In the current research, Academic Achievement is defined as the scores obtained by VIII and IX standard students in the annual examination held in March / April 2019.

CBSE Schools

The Board witnessed rapid growth and expansion at the level of Secondary education resulting in improved quality and standard of education in institutions. The Board was given its present name 'Central Board of Secondary Education'.

III. Research Design

Research Method

The study was undertaken using a descriptive method which attempts to describe and analyze the present conditions, with a view to have an accurate picture of the present which in turn forms the basis for future planning and policy-making to develop 'self' and 'emotional intelligence' and thereby to improve their academic performance.

Sample

The sample for the study was drawn from the CBSE schools located in Dharwad district. The schools were selected using stratified random sampling technique. Stratification was based on gender (boys / girls) and location (urban/ rural). For the present study around 10 urban schools and 10 rural schools were selected. From each school, about 40 – 50 students studying in X standard were selected. The total sample for the study was 600 CBSE school students drawn from 20 CBSE schools in Dharwad district.

Tool Used

For the purpose of the present study, the investigator used Sevenfold Emotional Intelligence Scale constructed and validated by Sarabjit Kaur (1996). The reliability of Sevenfold Emotional Intelligence Scale was established by test-retest method. The reliability coefficient between the two sets of scores was found to be 0.91, which is significant at 0.01 level significance. The validity of SEIS was taken into consideration by two ways 'experts opinion' and 'item analysis'.

Collection of Data

The investigator visited CBSE schools of Dharwad district with the permission of the heads of the institutions. The students were given necessary instructions about the various instruments and motivated them to respond genuinely to all the items. The tools and personal data sheet was administered. The data on each variable will be properly coded for further analysis.

Statistical Technique

	Statistical Techniques	Purpose
1	t-test Analysis	In pursuance of the Objectives – 1 to 3, 't' test was used to find out the differences in the self, emotional intelligence and academic achievement in terms of demographic variables, namely, gender and location.

Analysis

Gender

- i. Comparison of Male and Female CBSE School Students in their Self, Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement

Table – 1 : Comparison of Male and Female CBSE School Students in Self, Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement

Variable	Gender	Mean	SD	SE	t-value	P-value	Signi.
Self	Male	102.53	10.48	0.57	0.8700	> 0.05	NS
	Female	103.27	9.83	0.65			
Emotional Intelligence	Male	111.42	13.87	0.80	4.5308	< 0.05	Yes
	Female	116.62	13.30	0.82			
Academic Achievement	Male	388.64	106.04	6.10	3.8589	< 0.05	Yes
	Female	420.11	84.33	5.21			

The obtained 't' value 0.8700 with respect to Self of male and female CBSE school students is lesser than the tabled 't' value (1.97) at 0.05 level. It is, therefore, concluded that the two groups do not differ significantly in respect to the variable under consideration. That is, the hypothesis that male and female CBSE school students differ significantly in respect of their Self is rejected. Further, it is noticed that mean of Self scores of female CBSE school students is greater than that of male CBSE school students. Hence, it is concluded that female CBSE school students are more prone to Self when compared to male CBSE school students.

The obtained 't' value 4.5308 with respect to Emotional Intelligence of male and female CBSE school students is greater than the tabled 't' value (1.97) at 0.05 level. It is, therefore, concluded that the two groups differ significantly in respect to the variable under consideration. That is, the hypothesis that male and female CBSE school students differ significantly in respect of their Emotional Intelligence is accepted. Further, it is noticed that mean of Emotional Intelligence scores of female CBSE school students is greater than that of male CBSE school students. Hence, it is concluded that female CBSE school students are more prone to Emotional Intelligence when compared to male CBSE school students.

The obtained 't' value 3.8589 with respect to Academic Achievement of male and female CBSE school students is greater than the tabled 't' value (1.97) at 0.05 level. It is, therefore, concluded that the two groups differ significantly in respect to the variable under consideration. That is, the hypothesis that male and female CBSE school students differ significantly in respect of their Academic Achievement is accepted. Further, it is noticed that mean of Academic Achievement scores of female CBSE school students is greater than that of male CBSE school students. Hence, it is concluded that female CBSE school students are more prone to Academic Achievement when compared to male CBSE school students.

Male and Female CBSE school students differ in their Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement, however, do not differ in their Self.

Location

ii. Comparison of Rural and Urban CBSE School Students in their Self, Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement

Table – 2 : Comparison of Rural and Urban CBSE School Students in Self, Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement

Variable	Location	Mean	SD	SE	t-value	P-value	Signi.
Self	Rural	100.92	9.77	1.12	1.9817	< 0.05	Yes
	Urban	103.24	10.16	0.46			
Emotional Intelligence	Rural	109.63	12.42	1.42	2.8646	< 0.05	Yes
	Urban	114.49	13.95	0.63			
Academic Achievement	Rural	399.68	96.13	4.35	2.2139	< 0.05	Yes
	Urban	426.27	105.39	12.09			

The obtained 't' value 1.9817 with respect to Self of rural and urban CBSE school students is greater than the tabled 't' value (1.97) at 0.05 level. It is, therefore, concluded that the two groups differ significantly in respect to the variable under consideration. That is, the hypothesis that rural and urban CBSE school students differ significantly in respect of their Self is accepted. Further, it is noticed that mean of Self scores of urban CBSE school students is greater than that of rural CBSE school students. Hence, it is concluded that urban CBSE school students are more prone to Self when compared to rural CBSE school students.

The obtained 't' value 2.8646 with respect to Emotional Intelligence of rural and urban CBSE school students is greater than the tabled 't' value (1.97) at 0.05 level. It is, therefore, concluded that the two groups differ significantly in respect to the variable under consideration. That is, the hypothesis that rural and urban CBSE school students differ significantly in respect of their Emotional Intelligence is accepted. Further, it is noticed that mean of Emotional Intelligence scores of urban CBSE school students is greater than that of rural CBSE school students. Hence, it is concluded that urban CBSE school students are more prone to Emotional Intelligence when compared to rural CBSE school students.

The obtained 't' value 2.2139 with respect to Academic Achievement of rural and urban CBSE school students is greater than the tabled 't' value (1.97) at 0.05 level. It is, therefore, concluded that the two groups differ significantly in respect to the variable under consideration. That is, the hypothesis that rural and urban CBSE school students differ significantly in respect of their Academic Achievement is accepted. Further, it is noticed that mean of Academic Achievement scores of urban CBSE school students is greater than that of rural CBSE school students. Hence, it is concluded that urban CBSE school students are more prone to Academic Achievement when compared to rural CBSE school students.

Rural and Urban CBSE school students differ in their Self, Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement.

IV. Conclusions

1. Emotional intelligence and academic achievement of male and female students studying in CBSE schools differ each other, however, this difference is not significant in their development of self.
2. Urban and rural students studying in CBSE schools differ each other in their self, emotional intelligence as well as in their academic achievement.

V. Discussion

There are two types of emotional intelligence models identified in the related literature reviewed. In both the models, emotional intelligence has been defined as different constructs. The models are as follows : (a) Trait Models: Emotional Intelligence is correlated with personality traits (b) Ability Models: Emotional Intelligence includes the general measures of intelligence, coping abilities and regulation of emotions.

The famous EI models based on traits are : Goleman EI Model (1995) considered emotional intelligence as sum of personal and social competencies. Personal Competence guides us to manage ourselves whereas Social Competence guides us to handle our inter-personal relationships. Bar-On's Model of emotional intelligence (1997) was primarily based on the personality characteristics. He gave five areas of emotional intelligence which are Intra-Personal Skills, Inter-Personal Skills, Adaptability, Stress Management and Mood

in general. However, Bar One's model was criticized by giving the justification that these areas of emotional intelligence are not related with intelligence.

Ability EI models encompasses the emotion related cognitive abilities. This approach was originated by Mayer and Salovey. The four branch Mayer-Salovey model (1997) based on EI as ability is considered to be intelligence-based and ability-oriented approach. In contrast to EI Trait approach, the ability Emotional intelligence is defined as “the ability to perceive and express emotion, assimilate emotion in thought, understand and reason with emotion, and regulate emotion in the self and others” (Mayer & Salovey, 1997).

VI. Educational Implications

The concept of self is one which is vitally important to us from a psychological perspective because it is through the lens of the self that we view our world, navigate our lives, and create our narrative stories. Despite the importance of the concept of “the self,” because of the logical constraints we are faced with (namely our inability to obtain an objective standpoint when regarding the concept of ourselves) we will never be able to conclusively discover whether “selves” actually exist as things in themselves, I think it doubtful that they do and find it more persuasive that the concept of selfhood is nothing more than a psychological tendency. Despite this, *the appearance* of the self is something worth investigating. As I hope to have shown in this paper, the intuitive idea we have of the self as a persistent and ever changing entity is actually not what matters when we are talking about our vision of self. Instead, it is logically more likely that we are a bundle of successive selves connected by some direct relation, and it is actually the relation, rather than the unified consciousness, which is important when we are discussing selves. Further, the difference between the passing out of and passing into existence of a self, does not describe some deep metaphysical difference but rather simply is two different ways of describing one and the same outcome. Although at first disturbing, I believe this should give us a somewhat more optimistic outlook upon the time when we pass out of existence entirely, because perhaps it will not be as final as once thought, but rather a continuation of the cycle of self, continued without a physical vessel.

It is revealed from the research studies that students and parents recognized the emotional problems when individually interviewed but, they under played the need for help as reflected in very low rate of help seeking behaviour even when it was suggested and place of availability of help was properly informed. Therefore, there is need for proper sensitization of parents, teachers and students.

Academic success was also strongly associated with several dimensions of emotional intelligence and results were discussed in the context of the importance of emotional and social competency on academic achievement, in a study by Parker, James & Creque (2005) . In another study, Parker, Hogan, Easterbrooke *et al.*, (2006), examined the relationship between EI and academic retention. Participants were recruited during the first week of classes in the first year at the university and completed a measure of EI. Participants academic progress was tracked over the course of the year and students were divided into two groups. The first group consisted of students who withdrew from the university before their second year of study; the second group consisted of a matched sample of students who remained at the university for the second year of study. Results revealed that students who persisted in their studies were significantly higher than those who withdrew on a broad range of emotional and social competencies.

Achievement encompasses students ability and performance. It is multidimensional and is intricately related to human growth and cognitive, emotional and social development. Emotion is very important to the educative process because it drives attention which in turn, drives learning and memory. Our academic success may be related to the emotional status of the children. If children become unsuccessful in academic sphere, they become more and more frustrated and more maladjusted in other spheres of life. A number of studies suggest that emotional intelligence is associated with a range of positive outcomes. Emotional abilities are also likely to

be important for academic achievement (Salovey and Sluyter, 1997). The ability to manage emotions may help students to handle anxiety - arousing situations such as taking tests or starting creative projects.

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